

**SELECTION AND FOUNDATION OF POLYMER BINDER-FILLER
SUBSTANCES FOR HETEROCOMPOSITE POLYMER MATERIALS
USED IN MACHINE-BUILDING**

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Annotation: This article provides information on the selection and use of polymer filler substances for heterocposite polymer materials used in vehicles.

Key words: polymer material, cotton, composite materials, raw material, energy resource, mechanical engineering, epoxy resin, coating, coating, graphite, chlorinated polyethylene, silk processing waste, tribotechnical properties, friction.

It is important to improve the modern machine-building industry in the world, to create new advanced equipment, competitive and import-substituting technologies, machines and mechanisms for various industries, to conduct in-depth fundamental research, to address current scientific and technical issues [1,2,3]. Also, the targeted use of high-performance composite polymer materials to ensure the operational reliability of cotton processing machines is one of the current scientific and technical problems that need to be addressed to reduce the negative impact of technological equipment on cotton surfaces through the use of new materials. In this regard, research centers in developed countries, including the United States, Germany, Japan, Russia, China, Turkey and other countries, pay special attention to ensuring resource savings in the production of products from polymer composite materials [4,5,6,7,8].

The feasibility of structuring methods that allow the rational use of local raw materials and energy resources as an effective type of modification of heterocomposite polymer materials used in mechanical engineering is based [9,10]. Thermo-reactive binder epoxy resin ED-20-based composites and fillers for coatings as the object of study : coating, graphite, chlorinated polyethylene and silk processing waste (SWR) were obtained from local materials (Table 1).

Table 1

Materials selected for coating

No	Name of materials	GOST or TSH	Note
1	Epoxy resin (ED-20)	GOST 10587-72	Thermosetting binder ¹
2	Dibutyl phthalate (DBF)	GOST 8728-76	Plasticizer
3	Polyethylene polyamine (PEPA)	TIII 6-02-594-70	Hardener
4	Graphite (crumbly)	GOST 44404-88	Filler ($d \leq 20 \mu\text{m}$)
5	Angren kaolin	GOST 6138-61	Filler ($d \leq 20 \mu\text{m}$)
6	Silk processing waste (SPW), tester	UzDSt 993-2011	Filler ($d \leq 2 \text{mm}$)
7	Modifier Chlorinated Polyethylene (MChP)	UzDSt	Structural

1. Binder epoxy compound -EDk = ED-20 (100 tablespoons) + DBF (18 tablespoons) + PEPA (12 tablespoons)

As a model and control sample was taken a sample construction material - steel (St3), which is widely used in the working bodies of large-scale technological machines for processing cotton.

The following indicators of mechanical properties of samples were obtained in the accredited testing laboratory of Uz Dong Ju Paint Co. JV in Andijan, operating on the basis of ISO / MEK 17025: 2005 International and UzDST ISO / IEC 17025: 2007 Republican standards:

- HB-microhardness (hard meters №3635 ser. №3389 / 06 01.05.2019-01.05.2020) and PMT-3 equipment of Tashkent State Technical University;
- σ_{ud} - impact strength IMPAST TEST J-020 №5512 ser. №10-951 28.11.2018-28.11.2019;
- σ_{eg} - bending strength Bending Tester №5750 ser. №10-954 28.11.2018-28.11.2019;
- adhesion strength №315 ser 2236 28.03.2019-28.03.2020 adhesion meter;
- based on the method of unambiguous evaluation of the geometric dimensions of the coating №434817 ser. 3374 01.05.2019-01.05.2020 was determined using standardized methods and tools on the equipment of the testing laboratory. The error of the obtained results is guaranteed in the amount of less than 3% [11,12,13,14,15].

The tools and method of measuring adhesion strength, which are important for coatings, are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Tools and methods of measuring the adhesion strength of HCP coatings.

In the experiments, Andijan-36 and S-65-24 cottonseeds with air conditioning humidity of 8-12% and pollution of 3-12% were used.

The height of the stabilized surface roughness (R_z), the friction surface temperature (T_{tr}), the coefficient of friction as the main triboparameters (f), the relative mechanical damage of the cotton raw material to the metal surface (δ_0) and the linear abrasion intensity of the coating (I_l) were selected as control parameters.

The Lagrange interpolation formula and the specially developed program DGU 06756, 06757 were used to optimize the components and operational properties of the studied GKPM component and to process the research results [16,17,18].

The operational, i.e. tribotechnical properties of multifunctional HC polymer coatings and the relative mechanical damage of cotton are in accordance with the state standard (UzDST 2822-2014), first developed under the guidance of Professor U.A.Ziyamuhamedova. It has no analogues in the world, developed under the guidance of Professor A.B.Djumabaev (awarded the 1st place in the nomination "BEST USEFUL MODEL" IMFAP00782) by the IMA of the Republic of Uzbekistan [19,20].

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